

How INCLUDING is progressing?

A STEADY COMMITMENT FOR INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN UNION NUCLEAR SAFETY AND SECURITY

The last semester (August 2020 – January 2021) has been a fruitful time for the INCLUDING project, despite we are all living troubling days. All the different activities planned in the workplan progressed very satisfactorily and the project met all its contractual obligations with the European Commission for the period. Nevertheless, two moments were under the spotlights and namely the **Federation Open Day** (21st September 2020) and the **1st Annual Workshop** (08th October 2020). Both held online, the two events marked key contributions of INCLUDING in gathering together stakeholders to share views and thoughts on recent project developments and on up-to-date open issues in RN Safety and Security. The Federation Open Day, masterfully organized by Mrs R. Brancaleoni, Mrs M. Banaszek-Cymerman and Mrs M. Cimino, was largely conducted by Prof. S. Hadjiefthymiades (University of Athens) who described the structure and operativity of the INCLUDING web-based Platform, the innovative management tool for resources sharing in the Federation. The focal point of the presentation has been a practical example on how to plan a drill in a INCLUDING testbed and with mobilization of drones, robots and set of individuals (i.e. First Responders). The Federation Open Day was the occasion also to present the Mikkel (Finland) and Athens (Greece) testbeds that will be home to the next INCLUDING Joint Actions in April and June 2021, respectively and that will be described in this newsletter. The recording of the whole event is available under the 'Media' section of the INCLUDING website.

SUMMARY OF THE INCLUDING RECENT ACHIEVEMENTS

- *“Federation Open Day” online event*
- *“1st Annual Workshop” online event*
- *Report on international RN training programs by ISCC*
- *Presentation of INCLUDING at “Nuclear Power 1 Israel” On line international conference*
- *Presentation of INCLUDING to Polish policy makers, end users and industry during a conference on Crisis management aspects in national security management*
- *Release of the article “Tests and trainings included in response to Radiological and Nuclear threats” on NCT Magazine*
- *Release of the first two episodes of the comics series “Ross & Nate got included”*

The **1st Annual Workshop** has been broken down into two sessions. One restricted to project partners and selected invited participants, to assess the status of INCLUDING and ways forward. Another session was open to all stakeholders upon registration and during which a distinguished roster of panellists delivered speeches on different issues on Nuclear Security, Radiological Emergencies and application of nuclear technology in COVID 19 pandemic response.

Details on the open session of the Workshop are given in a devoted section of this newsletter.

INCLUDING has also intensified collaborations with other projects and, in this context, it is worth to mention the **H2020 project EU-HYBNET** and the **ESA project EuroSim**. In particular, INCLUDING is studying together EU-HYBNET common elements between nuclear security and hybrid threats in order to incorporate the findings in the next Joint Actions scenarios. Instead, together with EuroSim project, INCLUDING is jointly evaluating UrbanAware, an Incident Modelling Platform to provide lifesaving CBRN/HazMat situational awareness and decision support.

The dissemination activity of the project has been vibrant with the participation to the online international conference **“Nuclear Power 1 ISRAEL”** organized by the Ariel University. The INCLUDING coordinator was among the invited speakers and delivered a speech on how INCLUDING is contributing to improve collaboration between Member States on a sensitive matter like nuclear security. The presentation raised interest among the audience with a question from the USA during the Q&A session and gained also attention in an article of Nuclear World News Magazine. Remarkable was also the presentation of INCLUDING on December 2020 to Polish policy makers, end users and industry during a conference on **“Crisis management aspects in national security management system”**. Another achievement has been the release of the **‘Tests and trainings included in response to Radiological and Nuclear threats’** article and published in two parts on NCT Magazine. The main scope of the article is to make readers aware of the necessity of the radiological and nuclear (RN) training and establishing a unified and international RN crisis response. Finally, the INCLUDING Consortium is delighted to welcome on-board the project two new unusual members: Ross and Nate – two heroes of the brand new INCLUDING project comic **“R&N- Ross and Nate got included”**. With this new comic series, we are taking you back to the childhood. In each episode, R&N deal with nuclear and radiological challenges and take part in one of the event provided by INCLUDING Platform. You can follow Ross & Nate adventures on our project website.

THE 1ST INCLUDING ANNUAL WORKSHOP (OPEN SESSION)

INITIALLY PLANNED IN PHYSICAL PRESENCE, THE 1ST ANNUAL WORKSHOP OF INCLUDING HAS BEEN RESCHEDULED AS AN ONLINE EVENT AND WITH AN OPEN SESSION ON THE AFTERNOON OF 08TH OCTOBER 2020.

The open session of the 1st INCLUDING Annual Workshop was focused on three main sessions:

- Open issues in nuclear security with a focus on the status of the international activities, the management of a radiological crime scene and problems in medical aspects posed by specific scenarios.
- Recent events where radiation environmental monitoring has been key in assessing the possible onset of a radiological emergency.
- Possible use of assets and capabilities of RN domain for the support in countering COVID-19.

The first session was open by the speech of F. Padoani (ENEA - Italy) who revised strengths and weaknesses in the current global initiatives to bolster nuclear security. She sounded an alarm bell by reporting that experts' opinion and quantitative indicators clearly mark that nuclear security progresses have slowed down during the last two years and that the ongoing pandemic may lead to reduced regulatory oversight and to financial failure of the users to ensure safety and security of the radiation sources including disused radioactive sources.

The Workshop went on with the presentation of A. Liceia (Polícia de Segurança Pública - Portugal) on issues related to radiological crime scene management like conduct of operations, forensic evidences management and importance of international cooperation.

The first session was closed by a talk of Prof. D. Gui on medical aspects in RN emergencies, that is one of the main points of interest in INCLUDING. Prof. Gui put under deep scrutiny the in-hospital organization in case of RN emergency and with specific attention to the surge capacity. There have been, also, critically revised the lessons learnt in the Fukushima and Goiania accidents.

- nuclear security
- radiological emergency
- medical aspects of RN events
- management of a radiological crime scene
- radiation environmental monitoring
- assets and capabilities of RN domain for the support in countering COVID-19

On-line meeting

1. ANNUAL WORKSHOP

8th OCTOBER 2020
14:30 - 16:40

The second session started with a presentation from F. Rocchi and A. Cervone, both from ENEA, on the data analysis of environmental monitoring in Scandinavia during June 2020 when several stations in the Ring-of-5 and CTBTO (Comprehensive Nuclear-Test-Ban Treaty Organization) monitoring networks measured airborne fission and activation products, both short- and long-lived. The quantity of radioactive material was in the order of few $\mu\text{Bq}/\text{m}^3$ and it did not determine any significant impact on public health or the environment, nevertheless the nuclides are of artificial origin, so they must have been emitted from a man-made installation but nobody has claimed the responsibility for the release. Data analysis, using the backward trajectory methodology, allowed to pinpoint a general region where the release may have been originated.

In the successive talk, Capt. S. Kolovos, from the Hellenic Ministry of Defence, gave an overview of procedures at national and international level when dealing with a major blast involving radiological material. The presentation compared the EU, NATO and IAEA guidelines that each Member States is urged to adopt and with an explicative example for the Greek legislation actually in force.

It followed a practical case study presented by A. D'Angelo of SAFE (Italy) and related to the explosion at the Beirut port that happened on 04th August 2020. A radiological measurements campaign was carried out in the aftermath of the explosion to ascertain the accidental or voluntary involvement of radiological material.

The last talk of the workshop (third session) was from G. Marzo (ENEA) and on the role of ionizing radiations in support to the pandemic emergency response. The presentation highlighted how gamma ray irradiation from ^{60}Co sources has proven useful for sterilization or disinfection of personal protective equipment but in case of facemasks not for re-using.

The workshop was concluded with a Q&A session. The whole recording of the workshop and the slides of all the presentation are available on the INCLUDING website under the 'Media'.

We thank all the Speakers, Participants and our consortium Partners for a successful Annual Workshop!

PRESENTATION OF THE JOINT ACTION IN MIKKELI (FINLAND) – 19/22 APRIL 2021

AMID UNCERTAINTIES DUE TO THE EVOLUTION OF THE COVID 19 PANDEMIC, THE SOUTH SAVO REGIONAL FIRE SERVICE OF MIKKELI IN FINLAND IS ORGANIZING A TECHNICAL FIELD EXERCISE THAT IN THE WORST CASE SCENARIO WILL TAKE PLACE AS A FULL FINNISH EVENT.

The South Savo Regional Fire Service (SSAV) is the main organizer of the 2nd INCLUDING Joint Action, a Field Technical Exercise (FTX) that will take place in Mikkeli (Finland) from 19th to 22nd April 2021. The FTX will be a multi-agency coordinated response to a R/N incident scenario caused by stolen and missing Caesium-137 orphan source, which is a radioactive isotope of caesium. In the simulated scenario various civilians are exposed accidentally to radiation sources with irradiation and contamination. In addition to SSAV, several other local authorities, like the Eastern Savo Police Department, the Emergency Medical Service with the local hospital, Finnish Defence Forces and the Voluntary Rescue Service will be involved in the hazardous situation management. The FTX is organized with the support of Mikkeli Development Miksei Ltd., the City of Mikkeli and the Finnish Radiation and Nuclear Safety Authority (STUK). Much appreciated is the voluntary contribution of Environics and Mirion as technology providers of innovative tools to be deployed and tested during the FTX. In particular, the Mikkeli FTX has the scope to identify areas for improvements in dealing with a radiological emergency on a provincial/regional scale. It is focused on testing the capacity of the SSAV and Mikkeli area Testbed to sustain the development of the INCLUDING Federation seen as a network of practitioners in the RN sector and aimed at improving resources and knowledge sharing, adoption of best practices and interoperability at EU level. The scenario is tailored on a nuclear security event, like in the IAEA definition, and focused on the detection of Material Out of Regulatory Control (MORC). The FTX is expected to contribute to further develop a Nuclear Security Detection Architecture in Member States.

Mikkeli is a town and municipality in Finland. It is located in the province of Eastern Finland and is part of the Etelä-Savo region. The municipality has a population of 52,962 (around 34,000 in the town itself) and covers an area of 3,229.57 square kilometres of which 424.7 km² is water. The population density is 31.16 inhabitants per square kilometre. The town is located on lake Saimaa.

Mikkeli was the site for the headquarters of the Finnish armed forces during World War II. In recognition of this, the town's coat of arms incorporates a pair of crossed Marshal Mannerheim's batons, and the town was awarded the Cross of Liberty, 4th class, to be displayed with the coat of arms.

Mikkeli coat of arms

PRESENTATION OF THE JOINT ACTION IN PALASKAS (GREECE) - 22/23 JUNE 2021

ILLCIT TRAFFICKING OF RADIOLOGICAL MATERIAL IS A SERIOUS THREAT FOR THE EUROPEAN UNION. SEA LINES AND PORTS ARE THE PREFERRED TRANSFER ROUTES OF NETWORK OF SMUGGLERS.

The Hellenic Ministry of Defence organizes at the Palaskas training centre, in the western Athens outskirts, the **3rd INCLUDING Joint Action** and from **22nd to 23rd June 2021**. The Joint Action will consist of a multidisciplinary field exercise (MFE) dealing with counteracting an attempt to smuggle radioactive sources from the Palaskas port. During the exercise it will be conducted extensive use of UAV/UGV technology, and it will be checked the interoperability of the tools shared in the Federation. It will be a full-scale exercise designed to establish a learning environment for participants to be trained in emergency response plans, policies, and procedures in such situations. The risk of illicit trafficking of radiological material remains a potential threat to European security. The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) defines such practice as “the receipt, possession, use, transfer or disposal of radioactive material without authorization”. In this context, maritime routes and designated point of entry, like ports, are “hot spots” which deserve effective plans for resources mobilization to detect this Material Out of Regulatory Control and respond to eventual radiological contamination.

The Joint Action will test procedures and operational equipment deployment for command and control, communications, hazard identification, site security, monitoring and control of contamination and device recovery, packaging and custody for forensic evidences. There will be an extensive sharing of resources provided by members of the INCLUDING Federation in order to comply with EU and IEAE recommendations to enhance the level of international collaboration in the preparedness phase of nuclear security regime.

Athens is the capital and largest city of Greece with over 4 million residents. It has been inhabited since the Neolithic age (4000 BC) and reached its zenith in the 5th century B.C “Golden Age of Pericles”. Over the years, a multitude of conquerors occupied the city and erected splendid monuments of great significance. During the Middle Ages, the city experienced decline and then recovery under the Byzantine Empire. After a long period of decline under the rule of the Ottoman Empire, Athens re-emerged in the 19th century (1834) as the capital of the independent Greek state.

Palaskas training center consists of a large open military area next to the sea, located on the western outskirts of Athens. It belongs to the Navy providing training to its personnel on several domains.

TECHNICAL CORNER: EVA MAPS TRAINING

CRISIS MANAGEMENT TRAININGS USING WEB PLATFORM PROVIDE MORE PRACTICE OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE CRISIS RESPONSE TEAMS. THE NUMBER OF CONDUCTED EXERCISES SIGNIFICANTLY INCREASES THE PROBABILITY OF CALM JUDGMENT AND THE APPLICATION OF BEST PRACTICES.

Conducting emergency drills in a real environment require a lot of efforts and resources. This often may result in the limited number of emergency exercises carried out by organisations. Due to this limited number of possibilities for carrying out rescue exercises, the content of the exercises may only focus on common cases, excluding the rare ones. This, in turn, influences the crisis management teams' capacity.

The way to reduce these limitations and at the same time enable crisis management teams to build competencies and learn new methods and tools is to use the WEB platform to conduct the emergency exercises in the online mode. An example of such a system is the Astri Polska tool - EvA Maps Training 4.0.

EvA Maps Training 4.0. is a WEB platform developed for the needs of preparing and conducting simulation training in the field of coordination of activities during crisis events. Users benefit from being immersed in crisis scenarios and practising their response, bringing them face-to-face with crisis. The application is built in a mapping environment, adapted to the processing and visualization of geospatial data (GIS).

EvA Maps Training 4.0 allows to build any interactive scenarios using multimedia materials, in which many task groups can participate simultaneously. The trainer manages the sequence of events appearing in the scenario to which the trainee should respond appropriately. The order and frequency of events are adjusted to the involvement and pace of work of the participants and the predetermined difficulty of the scenario.

MEET THE EXPERT: DR FRANCA PADOANI

ADVISOR TO THE ITALIAN MINISTRY OF FOREIGN AFFAIRS AND INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION ON SAFETY, SECURITY AND NON PROLIFERATION; SOUS-SHERPA FOR THE 2016 NUCLEAR SECURITY SUMMIT AND ATTENDING NUCLEAR SECURITY CONTACT GROUP ACTIVITIES. MEMBER OF THE G7 NUCLEAR SAFETY AND SECURITY GROUP (NSSG) SINCE 2008 AND ITS CHAIR IN 2017. WORKING AT ENEA SINCE 1980, NOW IN CHARGE OF THE LABORATORY FOR DESIGN AND TECHNICAL SUPPORT FOR NUCLEAR SAFETY, SECURITY AND SUSTAINABILITY.

Dr Padoani, How strong is Global Nuclear Security nowadays?

The notion of Global Nuclear Security has been consolidated in the past decade, mainly thanks to the Nuclear Security Summit (NSS) process (2010-2016) and the commitments to strengthen nuclear security at the four Summits by the leaders of more than 50 States and International Bodies through the Communiqués, Work Plan and the Action Plans for the IAEA, UN, INTERPOL, Global Partnership Working Group (GPWG) and the Global Initiative to Combat Nuclear Terrorism (GICNT). Further commitments were also made by States or groups of States (known as “house gifts” and “gift baskets”), some of them transposed into IAEA INFCIRC. The ensuing achievements at national and international level have been outstanding, with a worldwide reduction of weapons-usable nuclear material and the increase of measures to protect nuclear and other radioactive material and associated facilities against the threat of theft or sabotage. Unprecedented efforts have also been made to ensure adequate capacity-building and to promote a nuclear security culture.

This positive trend in Global Nuclear Security is reflected in the NTI Nuclear Security Index, updated every two years since 2012 by the NTI with The Economist Intelligence Unit. This was the case at least until 2018, in fact the most recent index (July 2020) shows for the first time a slowdown of this trend, that more than one leading commentator considers to be evidence of the end of the NSS process. As stated by Ernest J. Moniz (former U.S. Secretary of Energy, 2013-2017):

Security improvements captured by the NTI Index between 2012 and 2018 reflected the work of the summits. Since the summit process ended in 2016, no comparable, cooperative global effort has emerged to replace the summits' role in galvanizing countries to take bold, ambitious actions.

The improvements are undeniable, and we are definitely in a much better position than a decade ago, but in many areas national implementation of nuclear security regimes is still weak. The political agenda appears to have shifted toward other priorities, but unfortunately, as long as major gaps exist in the global nuclear security architecture (for example, the insider threat, security culture at facilities, cyber security and radiological security) it is essential to maintain the level of attention not only to address known threats but also emerging threats that technology and nature continuously bring to the fore, most of which are completely unexpected.

What are the “hottest” topics in nuclear security?

Two high-level topics can summarize what is presently at stake.

The most important instruments in the international nuclear security legal framework are the Convention on the Physical Protection of Nuclear Material and Nuclear Facilities (2005 revision, CPPNM-A) and the International Convention for the Suppression of Acts of Nuclear Terrorism (ICSANT). The CPPNM-A is at present the only legally binding instrument for the protection of nuclear material and associated facility security. In 2021, five years after the entry into force required by the Amendment, there will be a Review Conference “to review the implementation of this Convention and its adequacy in the light of the then prevailing situation.” Many see the Review Conference as an opportunity to ensure high-level attention on nuclear security, lately showing signs of decline, as noted above. It will also be an important opportunity to share experiences and ideas in its implementation, including challenges, and possibly to decide the convening of regular Review Conferences to encourage country accountability and ways to adapt to evolving threats and technology, and to identify best practices.

The second topic is how to facilitate and update the national implementation of nuclear security systems, in particular through the possible revision of the IAEA nuclear security top-tier guidance in the Nuclear Security Series (Fundamental and Recommendations). After a long debate showing that the views of Member States range from no revision to full revision, the consensus appears to be for a limited revision to deal with unclear and inconsistent definitions, harmonize terminology, provide limited enhancements (e.g. computer security) and possibly add wording to address pandemics but without changing the overall scope and structure. The most critical document is NSS No. 13 “Nuclear Security Recommendations on Physical Protection of Nuclear Material and Nuclear Facilities (Infcirc/225/Revision 5)” which was meant at the time to reflect the CPPNM-A, while providing a revision of INFCIRC-225, but many feel that greater clarity is needed to better address new and emerging threats, safety-security interfaces, the definition of “Nuclear Facilities”, security planning, information protection, security during the lifetime of a nuclear facility, and sabotage thresholds. However, this document has served as the basis for many national regulations and bilateral or multinational agreements and any changes will have to be considered carefully.

What is the impact of the pandemic on nuclear security after a year?

One year after, unfortunately we are still not out of the pandemic. We are still dealing with its impact over a period probably much longer than most of us expected and still adapting at all levels to cope with it. So far, it seems that the nuclear sector has behaved well, showing resilience and a capacity to keep material and installations safe and secure while ensuring safe and secure operations, in spite of the difficulties arising from the availability of staff, maintenance glitches, information security issues, disruption of inspections, and so on. The system has responded well, but the difficulties are only expected to increase as the restrictions imposed in response to the pandemic are prolonged, activities that have been postponed need to be carried out, and the risk of Covid-fatigue grows. The IAEA has produced documents on the “Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Regulatory Activities for the Safety of Radiation Sources” (also dealing with security aspects) and, more in general, is at present collecting experience and lessons learned from Member States with a view to developing a Technical Report and the IAEA Nuclear Security Guidance Committee is considering guidance to be included in the Nuclear Security Series documents.

Addressing resilience and safe, secure and reliable operations during unexpected events, such as the pandemic, and carrying out in-depth studies on how to prepare and respond to parallel emergencies (CBRN or natural) is a priority and more guidance, based on collective experience, is of fundamental importance.

What is the role of education and training in planning and implementing sustainable nuclear programmes?

Sustainability remains one of the most critical aspects of a robust global nuclear security framework, and capacity-building is one of its essential elements. A deeply rooted nuclear security culture and adequate human resources at all levels – involving regulators, law enforcement agencies, academia, and industry – are universally recognized as the prerequisites for a robust and sustainable nuclear security regime, both national and global. At the same time, international cooperation and networks are fundamental elements in ensuring the development and sustainability of what may be called the “human dimension” of nuclear security, and the Nuclear Security Summit process has played a fundamental role in their consolidation.

From the analysis of the National Progress Reports at the last Nuclear Security Summit in Washington in 2016, over 40 countries reported that they were engaged in capacity-building either through training, Centers of Excellence (CoEs), or exercises.

Several commitments on capacity-building were actually made in the form of “house gifts” and “gift baskets” starting from the very first Summit in 2010, supporting increased awareness, nuclear security culture, and capacity-building through the setting up and promotion of Schools, CoEs, or Nuclear Security Training and Support Centers (NSSCs) and their networks. These constitute one of the most significant outcomes of the NSS process, and at present, nearly five years after the end of that process, they continue to be key assets in the development of a sustainable nuclear security architecture. For example, the number of NSSCs and COEs has steadily increased: at the end of 2020, the NSSC Network included 65 Members (73 Institutions) and 7 Observers with 37 operational Centres and 23 at the planning stage (see the IAEA Nuclear Security Information Portal NUSEC). In academia, the International Nuclear Security Education Network (INSEN), established in April 2010 to support the development of education programs in nuclear security, started with only a select group of universities and can now count on more than 60 members and 190 institutions. Regional approaches to capacity-building and nuclear security culture have also been fostered by the NSS process and several CoE/NSSC regional networks now exist, such as the Asia Regional Network (China, Japan, ROK) and the more recent Nuclear Security Support Centres Consortium created by Hungary, Lithuania and Ukraine (HLU Consortium). The European Union CBRN Risk Mitigation Centres of Excellences Initiative (EU CBRN CoE), through its regional approach, has a complementary and synergic role. In conclusion, capacity-building, encompassing education and training human resources, knowledge management and networks, is essential for a strong nuclear safety and security culture: providing support for capacity-building is fundamental for the sustainability of a national, and ultimately global, nuclear safety and security framework.

Dr Padoani, how do you think INCLUDING can help in building nuclear security?

INCLUDING is a well thought out project, designed to help strengthen national (and therefore regional and global) capacity by a team of extremely competent partners. I believe that its structure is particularly interesting and in the best position to help finding answer to some key questions that the pandemic has put in front of us:

- Study and invest more on emergency, preparedness and response, considering a combination of risks (CBRN and natural)
- Promote and develop training and exercises meant to be regular, realistic and adaptable, in order to increase resilience against unexpected events.

In a word, INCLUDING can help promote flexibility, probably the key word in the future.

ROSS & NATE GOT INCLUDED

RADIATION MEASUREMENT TRAINING

ROSS & NATE GOT INCLUDED

ONLINE TRAINING

THERE IS A FIRE IN NUCLEAR POWER PLANT

ROGER, SENDING ALL FIREFIGHTER UNITS THERE!

FIREFIGHTERS ARRIVED. FIFTEEN VICTIMS AND REACTOR BUILDING FIRE REPORTED

EXTINGUISH FIRE AND MEASURE RADIATION. SENDING AMBULANCE!

AMBULANCE ARRIVED. MEASURED RADIATION EXCEEDS ACCEPTABLE DOSE FIFTY TIMES.

SENDING ALL VICTIMS TO THE CLOSEST AVAILABLE HOSPITAL!

AMBULANCE SAFELY ARRIVED TO HOSPITAL. NOW TELL ME MY SCORE!

IT IS...30 PERCENT.

WHAT?! WHY IT IS SO LOW?

JUST TURN ON THE RADIATION CLOUD MODEL.

NOW YOU KNOW WHY?

YES, NOW I KNOW WHY.

**ARE YOU BETTER CRISIS MANAGER THAN ROSS?
JOIN INCLUDING FEDERATION AND PROVE IT ON
[HTTPS://INCLUDING-CLUSTER.EU](https://including-cluster.eu)**

JOIN INCLUDING COMMUNITY

If you need more information about the project or would like to participate during the INCLUDING events and demonstrations activities, please don't hesitate do contact us!

Please, stay tuned on our project website and twitter channel for updates and registration procedures for the INCLUDING events!

● **Joint Action in Mikkeli (Finland) – 19/22 April 2021**

● **Joint Action in Palaskas (Greece) - 22/23 June 2021**

INCLUDING: INNOVATIVE CLUSTER FOR RADIOLOGICAL AND NUCLEAR EMERGENCIES

Horizon 2020, Topic SU-GM01-2018-2019-2020: Pan-European clusters of practitioners and other actors in the field of Security - Innovation clusters from around Europe managing demonstration sites, testing workbenches, and training facilities.

